

MATERIAL-ADAPTED DESIGN CONCEPTS FOR ANISOTROPIC WARP KNITTED MULTI-AXIAL REINFORCED COMPOSITE AND SANDWICH STRUCTURES CONSIDERING THEIR STATIC, DYNAMIC AND ACOUSTIC BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT: Anisotropic composite and sandwich structures with textile reinforcement are predestined for function-integrating lightweight applications based on their variably settable characteristics. These generally multi-layered structures give the possibility of synergetically fulfilling the high requirements concerning stiffness and strength as well as damping and acoustic quality.

A material-adapted design concept for anisotropic composites with warp knitted multi-axial reinforcement, first of all has to include the detailed determination of the anisotropic static and dynamic material property profiles. These data are needed in the form of so-called characteristic parameter functions for the analysis of the induced stress and strain fields. The static elastic properties are measured at the Institut für Leichtbau und Kunststofftechnik (ILK) in tension, compression and bending tests for different temperatures. For the determination of the dynamic material properties a specially developed resonance bending test stand has been used. The anisotropic mechanical material property profiles of various textile-reinforced composites will be discussed in this paper.

Especially for applications with strong demands on damping and noise reduction, hybrid multi-layered sandwich structures are often used, which consist of face sheets with high stiffness and viscoelastic core layers. Compared with conventional lay-ups, these sandwich materials offer good structural-dynamic and acoustic characteristics due to high shear deformation and damping effects. On the basis of extensive experimental and theoretical investigations extended analytical and numerical models have been developed, which offer the possibility to specifically tailor the static, dynamic and also the acoustic behaviour of composite and shear-elastic sandwich plates. Therefore, the design engineer is now able to estimate the mechanical as well as the sound radiation characteristics of complexly loaded anisotropic textile composite and sandwich structures already within the conceptual design phase.

KEYWORDS: Anisotropic textiles, structural-dynamics, acoustics, design, testing

INTRODUCTION

Lightweight structures for high-technology applications are increasingly build in the form of hybrid constructions using different multilayered anisotropic textiles due to the versatile property profile.

Especially for dynamically loaded structures, a multi-material design with high damping combined with low constructive weight and adequate stiffness is required [1, 2]. But in today's sophisticated applications, lightweight structures will also have to meet very high acoustic, low noise standards. Therefore, an efficient static, dynamic and acoustic analysis has to be included in the multi-material design process.

Especially, for a structural-dynamic and acoustic design of anisotropic composite and sandwich structures with textile reinforcement, not only the stiffness but also the damping properties of the layered heterogeneous textile composite material must be modelled [3,4]. This requires to develop novel approaches, which realistically consider the inhomogeneity and directional dependences of the layered textile structure, when calculating the natural vibration and damping behaviour.

In this paper, advanced methods will be presented, which offer the calculation of eigenfrequencies and eigenforms as well as material damping of modern warp knitted multi-axial reinforced composite plates. For the principal analysis of the sound radiation, numerical simulations using the coupled Finite Element and Boundary Element Method (FEM and BEM) as well as detailed experimental investigations inside a reverberant chamber have been performed. On this basis, the dynamic and acoustic behaviour of different textile-reinforced composite materials was determined including the damping effects. Here, the fibre and matrix materials as well as the fibre orientation have been found to be of great influence on the sound radiation of textile-reinforced composite plates. Additionally, the high modal damping clearly influences the vibro-acoustic behaviour of these multilayered composite structures. The developed simulation models and the performed experimental investigations allow a material-adapted and function-integrating design of textile-reinforced composites considering their static and vibro-acoustic property profile.

STATIC AND DYNAMIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITES

The static material parameters of different textiles have been experimentally investigated at the ILK for different CF- and GF-reinforced composites [5]. The determination of the dynamic properties was performed using an experimental resonance bending technique based on the Fast-Fourier-Transformation (FFT). The measured dynamic anisotropic material parameters build the basis for the later calculation of the vibro-acoustic property profile of the composite structures.

In the resonance tests, usually five specimens depending on the fibre orientation are examined. The necessary experimental program contains resonance tests of textile specimen with a fibre orientation of 0° , 45° and 90° . The EP-CF compounds were fabricated using prepreg-technology whereas the PEEK-CF composites were made of hybrid commingling yarn textiles (Fig.1). The manufacturing of the analysed structures was performed using a HT-autoclave or a HT-press.

Fig. 1: Warp knitted multi-axial layer made of CF-PEEK commingling yarn [6]

The evaluation of the tests is done in wide-range resonance diagrams as a concurrent analysis of the resonances with respect to frequency, order and mode. The peak frequencies and the damping of the different resonance points can be determined exactly with a special evaluation algorithm based on the adjustable frequency range of the frequency generator and an adapted window zoom of the FFT analyzer. Finally, the dynamic moduli are calculated with a specially developed software tool (details can be found in [4]).

The dynamic properties of the composites are visualized in Fig. 2. The polar diagrams show the dynamic *YOUNG's* moduli and the material dampings of the composites CF/PEEK, CF/EP and GF/EP versus the fibre orientation.

Fig. 2: Dynamic material properties of fibre reinforced composites versus fibre orientations

In the polar diagrams, the antagonism of the dynamic stiffness and the damping of the UD structure is illustrated very clearly. For $\theta = 0^\circ$ (on-axis loads), the damping is always at a minimum and *YOUNG's* modulus is at a maximum. In spite of the different damping values, the CFRP composites considered here exhibit a qualitatively similar damping behaviour with a maximum at fibre orientations between 30° and 75° .

EIGENFREQUENCY AND EIGENFORM ANALYSIS OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE PLATES

For the structural-dynamic analysis of anisotropic and hybrid composite structures the determination of the free vibration behaviour is of major importance due to the big influence of the eigenfrequencies and eigenforms on the resulting dynamic and acoustic properties, especially within the low frequency range [7]. Here, the developed material-adapted analytical simulation model includes the special deformation behaviour of anisotropic composite plates in dependence of different bearing conditions. Fig. 3 shows the geometry and the coordinate system of the composite plate model.

Fig. 3: Composite plate geometry

The formulation of the basic elasto-dynamic equations is performed on the basis of the *HAMILTONIAN* principal. Thus, the well-known *LAGRANGE* function is used

$$\hat{L}(\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t)) = \hat{T}(\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t)) - \hat{\Pi}(\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t)) \quad (1)$$

with

$$\underline{\hat{u}} = [\hat{u}_z \quad \hat{u}_x \quad \hat{u}_y]^T = [\hat{w} \quad \hat{u} \quad \hat{v}]^T .$$

Here, $\hat{T}(\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t))$ denotes the kinetic energy, $\hat{\Pi}(\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t))$ the elastic potential and $\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t)$ the vector of the deformations.

The kinetic energy of the analysed composite plates is given by

$$\hat{T} = \int_V \rho(z) \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\hat{u}}}{\partial t} \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\hat{u}}}{\partial t} \right) dV \quad (2)$$

with

$$\rho(z) = \begin{cases} \rho^{(k)} & \text{for } z_{k-1} \leq z \leq z_k \\ 0 & \text{others} \end{cases} ,$$

as the density of the k^{th} layer.

For the case of free vibrations and the assumption of hyper-elastic material behaviour the elastic potential is equal to the potential of the inner forces or the deformation energy \hat{U}

$$\hat{U} = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{ \hat{\sigma}_x \hat{\epsilon}_x + \hat{\sigma}_y \hat{\epsilon}_y + \hat{\tau}_{yz} \hat{\gamma}_{yz} + \hat{\tau}_{xz} \hat{\gamma}_{xz} + \hat{\tau}_{xy} \hat{\gamma}_{xy} \} dV . \quad (3)$$

Following the *HAMILTONIAN* principal the time integral of the *LAGRANGE* function (*LAGRANGE* functional) is stationary, which is equivalent to the variational formulation

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \hat{L} dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} [\delta \hat{T} - \delta \hat{U}] dt = 0 . \quad (4)$$

Taking into account the *LAGRANGE* variation $\delta \underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, t, t_1) = \delta \underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, t, t_2) = 0$ it follows from (4)

$$\delta \hat{U} + \int_V \rho(z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \underline{\hat{u}}}{\partial t^2} \right)^T \delta \underline{\hat{u}} dV = 0 . \quad (5)$$

Assuming the free deformation field $\underline{\hat{u}}(x, y, z, t)$ being stationary, it can be written as

$$\underline{\hat{u}}^*(x, y, z, t) = \underline{u}(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t} \quad \text{with} \quad \omega = \frac{2\pi}{T_p}$$

and (5) finally yields the variational equation for the spatial functions U and \underline{u} of the time-dependent deformation energy \hat{U} and deformation field $\underline{\hat{u}}$

$$\delta U - \omega^2 \int_V \rho(z) \underline{u}^T \delta \underline{u} \, dV = 0. \quad (6)$$

For the solution of (6) then the *RITZ* method is applied in combination with the First Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT). This leads to a system of homogeneous linear equations for the determination of the coefficients of the *RITZ* approach, which can be written as a characteristic equation of an eigenvalue problem

$$(\underline{K} - \Lambda \underline{M}) \underline{\eta} = \underline{0} \quad (7)$$

The calculation of the eigenvalues Λ and the eigenvectors $\underline{\eta}$ is done numerically by using standard algorithms.

For anisotropic multilayered composites, the analytical determination of the loss factor d_g is based on the concept of complex moduli, which results in complex parameters in the material laws, complex structural matrices $\underline{K}^* = \underline{K}' + i\underline{K}''$, and complex eigenvectors $\underline{\eta}^*$ as well as complex eigenvalues Λ^* . The loss factors are then calculated form

$$d_g = \frac{\Lambda_g''}{\Lambda_g'}. \quad (8)$$

EXPERIMENTAL VIBRO-ACOUSTIC INVESTIGATIONS

The determination of the vibro-acoustic property profile of anisotropic composite structures involves experimental investigations, which have to include structural-dynamic and acoustic measurements.

The structural-dynamic measurements were carried out using the Laser Scanning Vibration Interferometer (LASVI) technology, which is an advanced measuring system for the analysis of vibrating structures. Compared with conventional techniques using electromechanical sensors, the mass and eigenfrequencies of which have negative influence on the accuracy of the measurements, the LASVI method allows a contactless and highly exact determination of vibrational quantities and conditions.

The basic principle of the Laser Scanning method is the Laser Interferometry. As a laser source an HeNe-Laser is used, which emits coherent light of a wavelength of $\lambda = 0.316 \, \mu\text{m}$. This laser beam is splitted by a prism S_1 into two different parts, the measuring beam and the reference beam (Fig. 4). A detailed description of the system can be found in [7].

Fig. 4: Operating principle of the LASVI

The identification of the eigenmodes is done by a scanning system, which allows the vibrational modes to be detected on different places of the surface without any change of the measuring head.

Fig. 5 exemplarily shows a comparison of the analytical results with the eigenmodes measured by LASVI. Here, two eigenmodes of a multilayered textile reinforced composite plate ($[0/+60/90/0/-60/90]_s$) made of CF/PEEK hybrid yarn are presented.

Fig. 5: Comparison of measured and analytically calculated eigenmodes

Even for eigenmodes of higher order, an excellent agreement of experiment and theory has been found, what proves the high accuracy and practical usability of the developed analytical calculation method.

The acoustic investigations were carried out within a reverberant chamber (Fig. 6), which is a closed room built by acoustically rigid walls. The sound waves inside the reverberant chamber are reflected on all of the rigid walls, so that this multiple reflection and scattering creates a diffuse sound field. This diffuse sound field is then taken as the acoustic excitation of a test plate, which is clamped inside a rigid wall. This wall separates the reverberant chamber into two rooms, the so called transmitter hall and the receiver hall. Inside the transmitter hall, an acoustic sound source creates the diffuse sound field, whereas inside the receiver hall the radiation of the vibrating plate is the sound source.

Fig. 6: Principal drawing of the reverberant chamber

Due to the diffuse sound field in both of the halls, the energy of the sound waves is approximately preserved. Thus, a reverberant chamber can be used to determine the radiated sound power of acoustically excited structures inside the receiver hall. This sound power is an integral and spatially constant physical parameter and therefore a suitable acoustic design variable.

In order to identify the acoustic property profile of the investigated fibre-reinforced composites, the radiated sound power of different plate structures made of CF/PEEK, CF/EP and GF/EP have been analysed inside the reverberant chamber (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Radiated sound power levels of different fibre-reinforced composites

A comparison of the sound power levels of the different CF-reinforced composite plates shows the acoustic influence of the matrix material. In most of the 3rd octave bands the CF/PEEK compound radiates less sound power than the CF/EP compound. Especially, for the lower frequencies up to 2 dB lower sound power levels have been measured. In addition to these results, the performed measurements give an overview of the acoustic properties of the different fibres. In all investigated frequency bands, the GF/EP composite have been found to radiate less sound power levels than the CF/EP composite.

FINITE AND BOUNDARY ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

For a more detailed analysis of the vibro-acoustic behaviour of textile reinforced composites, numerical calculations on the basis of the Finite Element Method and the Boundary Element Method (FEM and BEM) have been performed. These calculations were carried out in the workstation pool of the ILK. For the structural-dynamic analysis, mainly the program packages I-DEAS and ANSYS were used and the acoustic analysis was performed using the special BE software SYSNOISE and I-DEAS VIBRO-ACOUSTICS.

As input data for the BEM, the structural Finite Element (FE) mesh is needed. This mesh is then converted into a Boundary Element (BE) mesh, which includes the eigenfrequencies and eigenmodes resulting from the previous modal analysis using the FEM. The acoustic quantities on the radiating surface and on specially located points (domain/field points) are computed. These field points are positioned inside the air volume, which surrounds the vibrating plate [9]. For the detailed analysis of the sound radiation, the values of the radiated sound power and sound pressure have been computed.

The special focus of the performed FE and BE calculations was on the identification of the influence of fibre orientation on the sound radiation of acoustically excited modes of fibre-reinforced composite plates. (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Influence of fibre orientation on the radiated modal sound power of unidirectionally reinforced composites (CF/PEEK)

The calculated eigenmodes¹ 1/1 and 1/3 of the CF/PEEK composite plate are shifted to higher frequencies for increasing fibre angles in combination with a reduction of the radiated sound power. In contrast to this, an increase of the fibre angle leads to lower eigenfrequencies and higher sound power levels for the eigenmodes 3/1 and 5/1. This clearly reveals the great influence of geometry and anisotropy on the radiated modal sound power of fibre reinforced composite plates.

Additionally, the anisotropic damping behaviour of textile-reinforced composites has been included in the calculation of the sound radiation (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9: Change of the 3D-distribution of the radiated sound pressure due to damping

Exemplarily, the excited surface velocity and the 3D-distribution of the radiated sound pressure field of a textile reinforced composite plate have been calculated. Here, the sound pressure field has been found to be strongly influenced by the modal damping of the excited structural vibration.

The performed investigations show, that a material- and load-adapted design of anisotropic textile composite structures is only possible, if a detailed structural-dynamic and acoustic analysis is done, which includes the anisotropic damping properties.

¹ The eigenmodes of the analysed rectangular composite plates are named according to the number of deflection maxima, beginning with the longer edge.

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